

Experimental investigation of humidified air condensation in different rows of serpentine heat exchanger – Cooling water flow rate effect

Robertas Poškas^a, Arūnas Sirvydas^a, Mohab Salem^a, Povilas Poškas^a, Hussam Jouhara^{b,*}

^a Nuclear Engineering Laboratory, Lithuanian Energy Institute, Breslaujos 3, LT-44403 Kaunas, Lithuania

^b Heat Pipe and Thermal Management Research Group, College of Engineering, Design and Physical Sciences, Brunel University London, Uxbridge UB8 3PH, UK

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Condensation
Humidified air
Crossflow
Cooling ratio
Local heat transfer

ABSTRACT

Condensing economizers are used in the industry as they enable the acquisition of additional heat during vapor condensation. In condensing heat exchangers, water is the usual cooling agent due to its high specific heat capacity and thus efficient heat removal. Therefore, experiments of hot humid air condensation in a serpentine economizer being cooled by water were performed to reveal the effect the cooling water flow rate has on humidified air condensation in separate rows of the serpentine type economizer (with vertical tubes). The results have shown that the cooling ratio (mass flow ratio between the coolant and the humid air) had a minor effect on the distribution of the humidified air temperature along test section for inlet Reynolds number of 3000–10000. The effects on the condensation flux distribution in different rows were much stronger. The most optimal cooling ratio was determined to be 3. The results have shown that the biggest condensation efficiency is up to 35%. It was revealed that in some cases the convection was prevailing in the first rows of the economizer and this resulted in a decreased efficiency/performance of the exchanger.

The obtained results from the practical point of view will provide an extended basis for the optimisation of the design of economizers for waste heat recovery in the cases of different cooling water flow rates. It could also be applied to validate computational models developed for condensation heat transfer and condensate flux numerical modelling along economizer.

1. Introduction

There is an aspiration that the production processes of industrial companies operate as efficiently as possible and do not generate waste (heat, material) flows. In reality however, waste heat is generated in most industrial processes (oil and steel industries, chemical industries, laundries, wastewater treatment systems, etc.) and public facilities (computer centres, metro/train stations, service sector buildings, etc.). Efficient process production and the reduction of waste is intensively promoted by the European Union with the result that the implemented projects would lead to increased energy efficiency in the industrial sector, reduced CO₂ emissions in the short-term and long-term perspective and a saving in primary energy quantities. Depending on the temperature of the supplied waste heat, it can be used for different needs [1–3], for example, for premises heating or ventilation or for water preparation. If the temperature of the waste heat is too low, high-temperature heat pumps can be used to raise it. A very important aspect is the quality of the waste heat, i.e., its chemical composition,

mechanical contamination and the amount generated over time. Equally important is the ability to absorb this heat depending on the layout of nearby devices. According to all these parameters condensing heat exchangers are designed and selected with the intention of collecting waste heat [4,5] and improving of energy efficiency being the most interesting topic in the modern industrial era. The operation efficiency of heat exchangers depends on various factors. The most important of these are the geometry of the heat exchanger, the heat-exchanging surfaces and the operational parameters of the fluids. The features of the improvement of energy efficiency are considered in many papers [6–9]. The features include using tubes of various shapes, ribbed tubes, changing pitches of the tubes, adjusting certain flow, parameters, etc.

The first studies were mainly focused on the condensation of pure water vapor on various surfaces [10–12], etc., horizontal and vertical tubes and tube bundles [13–17], etc. However, there is also a possibility of condensing not only pure water vapor but also water vapor containing a large amount of non-condensable gases. This is especially important in power plants that incinerate various fuels and where the amount of water vapor mass fraction (WVMF) in the gases released into the

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Hussam.Jouhara@brunel.ac.uk (H. Jouhara).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsep.2024.102814>

Received 27 May 2024; Received in revised form 18 July 2024; Accepted 14 August 2024

Available online 15 August 2024

2451-9049/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Nomenclature		SHE	Serpentine heat exchanger
c_p	Specific heat, kJ/(kg·°C)	WVMF	Water vapor mass fraction, %
d	Outer diameter of the tube, m	<i>Subscripts</i>	
G	Volumetric flow rate, m ³ /s	c	Convection
l	Length, m	cd	Condensate/condensation
m	Mass flow rate, kg/s	cw	Cooling water
Nu	Nusselt number	dp	Dew point
P	Pressure, hPa	f	Fluid
Pr	Prandtl number	i	Local (row)
R	Cooling ratio	in	Inlet
Re	Reynolds number	out	Outlet
r	Latent heat of condensation, kJ/kg	ln	Logarithmic
S	Area, m ²	min	Minimal
t	Temperature, °C	t	Total (condensation and convection)
Q	Heat quantity, W	s	Saturation
q	Heat flux, W/m ²	v	Water vapor
<i>Abbreviations</i>		w	Wall
AH	Absolute humidity, g/m ³	<i>Greek symbols</i>	
CW	Cooling water	α	Heat transfer coefficient kW/(m ² ·°C)
CWFR	Cooling water flow rate, kg/h	η	Efficiency, %
DP	Dew point	λ	Thermal conductivity, kW/(m·°C)
RH	Relative humidity, %	μ	Dynamic viscosity, kg/(m·s)
HA	Humidified air	ρ	Density, kg/m ³

atmosphere could be from about 4 % to 30 % [18,19].

Results of the convection-condensation Nusselt number in horizontal tubes ($\varnothing 20 \times 2$ mm, 70 pcs. with longitudinal pitch of 40 mm) of a heat exchanger in crossflow were presented in [20]. In order to determine the effects of the gas Reynolds number and WVMF on the total heat transfer coefficient experimental investigations were performed in the simulated gas inlet Reynolds number range of 3000–6000 and inlet temperature range of 150–250 °C. It was noted that at the gas Re number equal to 3000, the total Nu number was about 45, while the Nu number in the case of air (i.e. without condensation) was only 25. The increase in Reynolds number to 6000 resulted in the total Nu number increase up to 80, while in the case of the air, it increased to 40. The total heat transfer coefficient increased with the increase in the flue gas flow rate (Reynolds number). Rather limited data for different rows of the heat exchanger demonstrated that in the analyzed gas Reynolds number range the total heat transfer coefficient was the smallest at the beginning to almost the middle of the heat exchanger and it varied between 100–125 W/(m²·°C). However, total heat transfer coefficient rapidly increased from the middle to the end of the heat exchanger – from about 125 W/(m²·°C) till almost 300 W/(m²·°C). The authors explained that this was because the water vapor fraction was decreasing continuously, saturation temperature was also decreasing and, in contrast, the gas temperature was decreasing more rapidly. Finally, it was proposed to calculate the total Nu number as a function of the gas Re number, Prandtl number and a condensation heat transfer factor [20]. So in general, paper [20] presents rather limited data on the operation performance of a heat exchanger by varying only a few parameters.

Another paper [21] presented the results of investigations of total heat transfer performed on a bundle of horizontal tubes ($\varnothing 20 \times 2$ mm, 180 pcs. with longitudinal and transverse pitches equal to 40 mm). The WVMF in the moistened air during the experiments ranged from ~ 3 % to 13 %. The moistened air inlet temperature was ~ 106–155 °C and Re = 3900–7300. Investigations were also performed to examine the total heat transfer in relation to various parameters. It was found that the total Nusselt number almost linearly increased as the moistened air inlet Reynolds number increased. A similar dependency of the total Nusselt number on an increase in the WVMF was also seen, where the total

Nusselt number increased from 40 till 150 when the WVMF was increased from 3 % to 13 % at the Re number of 5600. During this study it was shown that an increase in the WVMF had no effect on the convection heat transfer coefficient, and therefore it remained almost constant at the value of about 40 at Re = 5600. Nevertheless, the overall heat transfer coefficient increased rapidly once the WVMF was increased. The results have demonstrated that change of the WVMF from 3 % to 13 % gave an increase in the overall heat transfer coefficient of up to ~ 3.5 times compared to the case of forced convection without condensation. Based on the experimental results and the theoretical analysis, the authors proposed an augmentation factor and a generalizing formula for calculation of the overall Nu number as a function of the Re number, Prandtl number and augmentation factor. However, the influence of the coolant flow rate was not analyzed.

Flue gas condensation characteristics in a vertical narrow gap heat exchanger composed of three narrow bundles were investigated experimentally in [22]. In order to reveal the effects of the cooling water flow rate (CWFR), flue gas velocity and temperature on condensation and the total Nusselt number, the investigations were performed in the flue gas inlet Re number range 1400–2500, condensation factor range of 0.2–1.2 and flue gas inlet temperature to the heat exchanger of 60–90 °C. The results showed that the CWFR and temperature had a significant effect on heat transfer. The condensation efficiency when the cooling water inlet temperature was 20 °C, increased from almost 40 % to about 55 % as the CWFR increased from 0.2 m²/h to 0.8 m²/h. The increased cooling water temperature from 20 °C to 35 °C gave the opposite effect – the condensation efficiency decreased to 25 % and 35 % for the same range of the CWFR. The convection heat transfer coefficient remained almost constant with the value of about 55 at different CWFR and temperatures; however, the total heat transfer coefficient was gradually increasing with the increasing CWFR and was decreasing with the increasing cooling water temperature. After the experimental investigations the authors proposed a generalizing correlation for the estimation of the average Nu number in the range of experimental parameters with the uncertainty within ± 10 %.

A numerical analysis of the influence of relative humidity on the change of the total Nusselt number in humid air $5000 < Re_{in} < 20000$

over vertical elliptical tubes (tube cross section 14.3x3 mm) in staggered configuration of seven rows was done in [23]. The analysis was performed at a humidified air inlet temperature of 50 °C, by changing the relative humidity from 10 % to 90 % which, during the investigations, corresponded to changing the mass fractions of water vapor from about 1 % to 9 %. It was found that, by changing the relative humidity from 10 % to 90, the increase in the Nusselt number of humid air in comparison to that at dry air % was from 1 % to about 4.5 %, respectively. This was true for the whole range of humid air inlet Reynolds numbers. Finally, it was concluded that for the range of the Reynolds number analysed, the change in the Nusselt number was mainly due to the change in humidity content of air that was observed independent of the Reynolds number. The data on the effect on the total Nu number for different humidified air inlet temperatures and CWFRs was not presented.

Effects of various parameters on condensation of the humidity existing in flue gas in three vertically staggered tube bundle heat exchangers connected in a series was analysed in [24]. The vertical tubes used in the heat exchangers were $\varnothing 12 \times 1$ mm with transverse and longitudinal pitches of 20 mm. Each condenser was composed of 6 transverse and 12 longitudinal rows. During the experiments, the flue gas inlet velocity was varied from 2.5 m/s to 7 m/s, the water mass fraction was in the range 4–16 % and the CWFR was changed from 3.3 l/min to 16.5 l/min. The results showed that in each heat exchanger the dry air heat transfer coefficient was similar and with increased flue gas velocity it was almost linearly increasing from about 65 W/(m²·°C) to 100 W/(m²·°C). The total heat transfer coefficient was at least twice as high as the convective heat transfer coefficient and its increase was observed with the velocity increase from 2.5 m/s to about 4 m/s. With any further increase in the velocity from 4 m/s to 7 m/s the total heat transfer coefficient started to decrease. The reason for the decrease at a higher velocity was the shorter residence time of the humid flue gas in a heat exchanger as some humidity was driven away from it. The condensate flux dependency on the analysed flue gas velocities for different water vapor amounts in flue gas showed a gradual increase in the condensate flux when the WVMF was increasing from 4 % to 12 %. A further increase in the vapor fraction to 16 % gave a gradual reduction in the condensate flux at all analysed flue gas velocities. This was because the condensers were unable to condense the increased proportion of water vapor in flue gas. During the investigation, the highest condensation efficiency of about 50 % was reached at the smallest flue gas flow velocity (2.5 m/s) and a WVMF of 12 %. With the increase in the flue gas velocity to 7 m/s the condensation efficiency at the same WVMF=12 % decreased to 20 %.

The effect of cooling agent parameters on the total condensation efficiency of six vertical tubes bundle heat exchangers (composed of $\varnothing 12.7$ mm tubes, with transverse and longitudinal pitches of 0.7 and 2, respectively) connected in a series was analysed in [25]. The change of the ratio between the coolant and the humid flue gas flow from 1.5 to 2 had no influence on the condensation efficiency as it remained almost constant at about 60 %. When the ratio was 3 the condensation efficiency increased to about 70 %. At a higher ratio (ratio 4), the condensation efficiency remained the same as in the case of ratio 3. The inlet temperature of cooling agent was also an important parameter. The change of the coolant inlet temperature of about 10 °C (from ~ 25 °C to 35 °C) decreased condensation efficiency by almost 25 %, i.e., from 70 % to 45 %.

Experimental results in a tube banks heat exchanger ($\varnothing 9.5 \times 0.8$ mm with five tubes in transversal and fifteen tubes in longitudinal direction) in the case of the mass flow rate of humid air in the range of 40–100 kg/h (70 °C) and CWFR 180–420 kg/h (25–35 °C) are presented in [26]. The researchers kept a constant WVMF in the air, i.e., at 10 %. It was found that, with an increase in the CWFR from 40 kg/h to 420 kg/h, the total heat quantity was transferred to the cooling water increased marginally – from 1.6 kW to ~ 1.85 kW. In this case, the sensible heat quantity released from humid air remained almost constant (~0.35 kW) and the increase in the heat quantity obtained by the cooling water was mainly

due to the release of latent heat. During the experiments an increase in the air flow rate from 40 kg/h to 100 kg/h resulted in constantly decreasing condensation efficiency: from 50 % to about 30 %. This was because the augmentation of the mass flow rate of the water vapor was more than the enhancement in the condensation flux. The change of the water flow rate from 180 kg/h to 420 kg/h (i.e., mass flow ratio between cooling agent and humid air changed from 2.25 to 5.25) did not give any substantial increase in the total condensate flux as it increased from about 25 % to 30 % and remained constant from the ratio of 4. No analysis of the influence of the WVMF was provided.

In another study, condensation of humid air with a vapor mass fraction of about 8–12 % and an inlet temperature of ~ 130 °C was analysed numerically in five vertical tubes bundle heat exchangers connected in series [27]. During this study only average characteristics of each of the heat exchangers were analysed. In the case of a low WVMF, there was no condensate collected in the first two heat exchangers. While in the case of a bigger WVMF, the condensation started already in the first heat exchanger. The condensate fluxes for both cases of WVMF from the heat exchangers were different. The condensate fluxes obtained rather well correlated with the experimental data. This study also led to a conclusion that the released latent heat of condensation slowed down the sensible heat release in the flue gas. Therefore, the temperature decreasing rate of flue gas with condensation was lower than that without condensation.

Recently, there were some investigations done on the condensation of water vapor (from flue gas, humid air) using ceramic membrane condensers [28,29]. The hot gas temperature and membrane pore size are the key factors that affect the condensation efficiency of the membrane condenser. Increasing the gas temperature cannot continue to increase the condensation efficiency and heat recovery efficiency. The convection Nu number during these experiments was increasing as the gas temperature increased from 50 °C to 80 °C, and the Nusselt number of the 10 nm pore size ceramic membrane increased from almost 42 to about 92, while the Nusselt number of the 3 μ m pore size ceramic membrane increased from 10 to about 31. The authors did not analyse any local parameters of such a heat exchanger. However, the use of ceramic membrane condensers due to their high price is still very limited. In summary the literature review shows that there are some rather limited investigations concerning the influence of gas and coolant parameters on the heat transfer and performance of horizontal and vertical tubes condensing heat exchangers. All the investigations concentrate mainly on total heat transfer characteristics which are not enough to provide the real picture of the processes occurring locally in heat exchangers. Therefore, the current study presents the investigations of the operational parameters variation of the humidified air (inlet Reynolds number, temperature, water vapor mass fraction) and water cooling agent (flow rate) on the local heat and mass transfer performance in a serpentine type (mostly with vertical tubes) heat exchanger (SHE). The quantification of the effects and the mapping of the distribution of heat transfer behaviour in each row of the bundle presented in this paper give a novel contribution on the processes occurring in different rows in heat exchangers. Findings of the study will also provide a solid ground for the improvement and refinement of the design of condensing economizers. The study results can also serve as validation for condensate process modelling in heat exchangers and numerical solutions developed for condensation heat transfer.

2. Experiments

Fig. 1a presents the experimental setup, with the following main components: a serpentine type heat exchanger (SHE, i.e. the test section) (9), compressor for air supply (1), heaters for heating of the air being supplied (3), steam generator for the generation of water vapor (7) and cooling water lines for the cooling of the SHE. In order to ensure the airflow stability through the SHE, air from the compressor was reached air reservoir and then directed to the heaters. From heaters the hot air

Fig. 1. Experimental setup with test section (a): (1) compressor, (2) air reservoir, (3) air flow rate meters, (4) air heaters, (5) air and water vapor mixing chamber, (6) vapor flow rate meter, (7) steam generator, (8) large diameter tube, (9) test section (SHE), (10) serpentine tubes bundle, (11) bottles for condensate collection, (12) stack; SHE with the tubes bundle, bottles for condensate collection and temperature measurement points (b).

flew into the mixing chamber. Water vapor from steam generator was also transferred to the same chamber. The resulting humidified air (HA, i.e. a mixture of air and water vapor) was routed to the SHE through a large diameter ($\varnothing 271 \times 4$ mm) tube.

The details of SHE are presented in Fig. 1b. The SHE was designed by the Lithuanian Energy Institute in cooperation with Brunel University London. The SHE was composed of 3 serpentine stainless-steel tubes (each $\varnothing 18 \times 2$ mm) embedded in a metallic rectangular housing. On the walls, half-serpentine tubes were fixed but they were not cooled by water. The transverse and longitudinal pitches of the bundle were 1.5 and 7.2, respectively. The total heat transfer area of the tubes bundle in the SHE was 0.49 m^2 .

All the measurement equipment used for the experiments was calibrated. For the measurement of the air and water steam flow rates, respective flow rate meters were used (E+E Elektronik, Austria and Sierra Instruments, USA, accuracies $\pm 3.3\%$ and $\pm 1.5\%$, respectively). The necessary WVMF in the air supplied to the SHE was controlled by regulating the flow rates of the air and water vapor. At the outflow of the SHE, the gas was discharged into the atmosphere through the stack.

The temperatures in the test section (tube wall, HA and CW) were determined using chromel-copel-type thermocouples (wire diameter 0.2 mm, accuracy $\pm 0.3\%$). For the collection of the data from the thermocouples Keithley data acquisition system was used (accuracy $\pm 0.25\%$).

The cooling water flow was adjusted through each serpentine tube of the heat exchanger by valves, and its flow rate was measured using water flow rate meters (Isomag, Italy, accuracy $\pm 0.4\%$). The cooling water inlet temperature during all the experiments was 7–8 °C. The cooling water and HA were flowing in counter-current directions.

The collection of the condensate along the SHE was realised in four bottles (i.e. from rows 1 + 2, 3 + 4, 5 + 6 and 7 + 8, see Fig. 1). Each empty bottle before the experiment and the bottles with the condensate after the experiment were weighted on the scales (Beurer, accuracy ± 1 g).

More details about the experimental setup and measurement equipment used during the experiments are provided in [26].

3. Methodology

Usually, water vapor mass fraction in released flue gases depends on the fuel being incinerated. It can be in the range of 4–13 % for coal, 10–15 % for natural gas and up to 30 % for biofuel. The temperature released from the boiler at the condensing heat exchanger could usually be between 80–180 °C or even more [16,18,19]. Therefore, experimental investigations were done at a few inlet Re numbers ($Re_{in} = 3 \times 10^3$, 5×10^3 and 1×10^4), a few gas inlet temperatures ($t_{in} = 85$ °C, 145 °C, 205 °C), two WVMFs (10 % & 20 %) and a few CW and HA flow ratios ($R=1$, 2, 3 and 4). The CW inlet temperature during all the experiments was about 7–8 °C. During the experiments, the pressure inside the SHE was close to atmospheric.

The local parameters were evaluated at each row along the SHE (they are given by index i of the specific row in the formulas presented further).

The following formula was used to calculate the local specific heat flux obtained by CW:

$$q_{ti} = Q_{cw_i} / S_i = \frac{m_{cw} (c_{p,cw_i} \cdot t_{cw_i} - c_{p,cw_{i+1}} \cdot t_{cw_{i+1}})}{\pi \cdot d \cdot l_i} \quad (1)$$

where Q_{cw_i} is the heat obtained by the cooling water, W; S_i is the outer surface area of the tubes, m²; m_{cw} is the cooling water mass flow rate, kg/s; c_p is the specific heat of the water at the outlet and inlet temperatures, kJ/(kg·°C); t_{cw} is the temperature of the cooling water, °C; d is the outer diameter of the tube, m; l is the length of the tube measured along the tube axis between the elbows of the tube, m.

To calculate the heat released due to HA cooling and water vapor condensation, the following formula was used:

$$Q_f = m_f \cdot (t_{f,in} \cdot c_{pf,in} - t_{f,out} \cdot c_{pf,out}) + m_{cd} \cdot r \quad (2)$$

where m_f is the HA flow rate, kg/s; c_{pf} is the specific heat of the HA, kJ/(kg·°C); m_{cd} is the condensate flow rate, kg/s; r is the latent heat of condensation, kJ/kg.

To calculate the local heat flux due to condensation, the following formula was used:

$$q_{cd_i} = \frac{m_{cd_i} \cdot r_i}{\pi \cdot d \cdot l_i} \quad (3)$$

To calculate the local heat flux due to convection, the following formula was used:

$$q_{ci} = q_{ti} - q_{cd_i} \quad (4)$$

To calculate the overall heat transfer coefficient (W/(m²·°C)) for each section of the SHE, the following formula was used:

$$\alpha_{ti} = q_{ti} / (t_f - t_w)_i \quad (5)$$

where t_f is the average of the HA temperature measured at the centre of the test section before and after a respective tube row, °C; t_w is the measured average outer tube wall temperature, °C.

The total (overall) Nu at each section was obtained as:

$$Nu_{ti} = \alpha_{ti} \cdot d / \lambda_i \quad (6)$$

Where λ is the thermal conductivity of the HA based on t_f , W/(m·°C).

To calculate condensation efficiency (%), the following formula was used:

$$\eta = (m_{cd} / m_{v,in}) \cdot 100 \quad (7)$$

where m_{cd} is the total water condensate flow rate, kg/s, $m_{v,in}$ is the water (as vapor) flow rate at the inlet into the test section, kg/s.

To calculate the average heat transfer coefficient, the following formula was used:

$$\bar{\alpha} = Q_{cw} / (S \cdot \Delta t_{ln}) \quad (8)$$

Where Δt_{ln} is the logarithmic mean temperature.

To calculate the Δt_{ln} , the following formula was used:

$$\Delta t_{ln} = \frac{(t_{f,in} - t_{cw,out}) - (t_{f,out} - t_{cw,in})}{\ln[(t_{f,in} - t_{cw,out}) / (t_{f,out} - t_{cw,in})]} \quad (9)$$

To calculate the average Nusselt number, the following formula was used:

$$\bar{Nu} = \bar{\alpha} \cdot d / \lambda \quad (10)$$

In formula (10), λ is for average HA temperature, calculated as $\bar{t} = (t_{f,in} + t_{f,out}) / 2$.

The HA inlet Reynolds number was defined from:

$$Re_{f,in} = \frac{G_{f,in} \cdot d \cdot \rho_{f,in}}{S_{min} \cdot \mu_{f,in}} \quad (11)$$

where $G_{f,in}$ is the volumetric HA flow rate, m³/s; S_{min} is the minimal flow area between the tubes, m²; $\rho_{f,in}$ is the HA density at the inlet to the test section, kg/m³; and $\mu_{f,in}$ is the HA dynamic viscosity at the inlet to the test section, kg/(m·s). The parameters in formula (11) are calculated based on the HA inlet temperature

The HA outlet Reynolds number was defined from:

$$Re_{f,out} = \frac{G_{f,out} \cdot d \cdot \rho_{f,out}}{A_{min} \cdot \mu_{f,out}} \quad (12)$$

The parameters in formula (12) are based on the HA outlet temperature.

Average Re number was obtained as:

$$\bar{Re} = \frac{Re_{in} + Re_{out}}{2} \quad (13)$$

The cooling ratio was determined as:

$$R = \frac{m_{cw,in}}{m_{f,in}} \quad (14)$$

The local WVMF was defined from the local HA flow rate (the collected condensate flow rate was taken into account). Dew point (DP) temperatures in each row of the SHE were defined from local WVMF and formulas presented in [30].

Saturation vapor pressure:

$$P_s = \left(6,089613 \cdot 10^{\frac{7,33502 \cdot t_f}{230,3921 + t_f}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (15)$$

Water vapor pressure:

$$P_v = P_s \cdot \frac{RH}{100} \quad (16)$$

where RH is relative humidity, %.

To calculate absolute humidity (AH), the following formula was

used:

$$AH = \frac{2.1667 \cdot P_v}{t_f + 273.15} \quad (17)$$

To calculate the dew point (DP) temperature, the following formula was used:

$$t_{dp} = \frac{230.3921}{\left(\frac{7.33502}{\log_{10} \left(\frac{P_v}{6.08961} \right)} \right) - 1} \quad (18)$$

4. Results and discussion

As discussed, the experimental tests were performed with different WVMFs (10 % and 20 %), different HA inlet temperatures (85 °C, 145 °C and 205 °C), inlet Re numbers (3000, 5000 and 10000) and cooling ratios (R=1, 2, 3 and 4) in order to reveal their effect on condensation in different rows of the heat exchanger.

4.1. Cooling ratio effect on condensation at WVMF=10 %

4.1.1. Reynolds number 5000, HA inlet temperature 85 °C

Fig. 2 shows local distribution of the surveyed parameters (collected condensate, water vapour mass fractions, temperatures, and relative heat flux variations) along the SHE mock-up when the HA inlet Re number was 5000, the HA temperature at the inlet was 85 °C and cooling ratios were 1 and 4.

The results showed that, for both cooling ratios, the HA temperature almost linearly decreased along the test section (Fig. 2a, curves 1 and 6). At the cooling ratio R=4, the HA temperature decreased slightly more in comparison to that at R=1 and, at the exit of the SHE (i.e., row no. 8), the difference among them was only about 2 °C (i.e., 62 °C for R=1 and 60 °C for R=4). Hence, in this case, the cooling ratio had no meaningful influence on the HA temperature distribution along the tube bundle. However, differences in the tube wall surface (Fig. 2a, curves 2; 7) and CW temperatures (Fig. 2a, curves 3 and 8) were more noticeable. The CW temperature was increasing from row no. 8 (CW inlet) to row no. 1 (CW outlet). At the smaller cooling ratio the increase was much larger (from 8 °C to 26 °C, i.e., difference 18 °C) than in the case of the larger ratio where it changed only from 8 °C to 12 °C (difference 4 °C). The character of the tube wall surface temperature variation when R=1 was very similar to the character of the CW temperature variation in the test

section. In this case, the temperature difference between the CW and tube wall temperatures (Fig. 2a, curves 2; 3) remained almost constant along the test section. At R=4 the water flow rate was much larger than at R=1 and, as a result, the tube wall temperature (Fig. 2a, curve 7) remained much smaller than that obtained at R=1 with the resulting difference between the tube wall and the cooling agent temperatures (Fig. 2a, curve 8) not being constant along the SHE.

DP temperature change along the tube bundle almost coincided for both cooling ratios (Fig. 2a, curves 5 and 10) but, in the case of R=4, a slightly bigger decrease was recorded at the end of the experimental section. In both cases, DP temperatures were higher than the tube wall temperatures and consequently condensation reaction took place in every row of the experimental test section (Fig. 2b). Similar tendencies concerning the DP temperature were also noticed for WVMF (Fig. 2a, dots 5 and 10). The differences in the WVMF started to occur from rows no. 3 and no. 4 and, at the end of SHE, the water vapour mass fraction decreased to 7.9 % and to 7.5 % in the cases of R=1 and R=4, respectively.

The condensate flux distribution (Fig. 2b) along the experimental section at both cooling ratios showed the same tendencies: in the first rows (rows no. 1 and 2) it was about 11 kg/(m²·h), in rows no. 3 + 4 it increased and then in rows no. 5 + 6 and no. 7 + 8 it started to decrease gradually. At higher cooling ratio the condensate flux was larger in rows no. 3 + 8 compared to that at the smaller cooling ratio.

Although the HA and CW were of the highest temperature at the inlet to the experimental section (rows no. 1 + 2) the conditions for condensation were still acceptable. Therefore, condensation took place here but the condensate flux was smaller than in other rows. In the next rows (rows no. 3 + 4) the temperatures of the wall surface and cooling agent dropped (see Fig. 2a) and a more intense condensation occurred. After that, the intensity of the condensation process dropped and the condensate flux started to decrease because mild condensation occurred in sections no. 1 + 4 and, although the tube wall and coolant were of even lower temperatures (rows no. 5 + 8), the difference in the HA and tube wall temperatures was smaller. A larger condensate flux at R=4 was received because the tube wall temperature remained smaller in comparison to that at R=1.

The ratio of convection to total (q_c/q_t) heat fluxes is presented in Fig. 2b. It is evident that, for both cooling ratios q_c/q_t at the beginning of test section, the convection heat flux is about 35 % from the total heat flux and then it decreases along the test section to 25 %. The obtained q_c/q_t ratio values (Fig. 2b) mean that the influence of the convection is smaller, and it decreases along the test section. Mostly the condensation is dominating and its effect is increasing through the test section.

Fig. 2. Temperature and WVMF (a), condensate flux and heat flux ratios (b) variation along the heat exchanger at Re_{in} = 5000, t_{in} = 85 °C, when the ratios of the cooling water flow rate to the HA inlet flow rate are R=1 (curves 1–5): (1) average HA temperature, (2) average outside tube wall surface temperature, (3) cooling water temperature, (4) WVMF, (5) dew point temperature; when cooling ratio R=4 (curves 6–10): (6) average HA temperature, (7) tube wall temperature, (8) cooling water temperature, (9) WVMF, (10) dew point temperature.

4.1.2. Reynolds number 5000, HA inlet temperature 205 °C

As the figure presented below (Fig. 3) shows the inlet parameters in this case were the same as presented in Fig. 2 with the exception of the HA inlet temperature, which was 205 °C. As in the previous case, the results indicate that the HA temperature changes (decreases) along the SHE and only slightly depends on the cooling ratio (Fig. 3a, curves 1 and 6). The CW temperatures (Fig. 3a, curves 3 and 6) are also increasing from the inlet to the outlet; however, as in the case of $R=4$, the flow rate is larger than in the case of $R=1$ and, as a result, it is smaller at the outlet. The temperatures of the tube wall surface temperature and CW (Fig. 3a, curves 2; 7) show very similar variation and the difference between them is almost constant through all the experimental section. When the HA inlet temperature $t_{in} = 205$ °C the temperatures of the CW and tube wall are higher by a few degrees compared to those for $t_{in} = 85$ °C.

As the HA temperature to the experimental section was higher (205 °C) the conditions for condensation were worse in comparison to those in the previous case when the temperature was lower (85 °C). Therefore, it can be seen that the decrease in the WVMF (Fig. 3a, curves 4 and 9) along the test section for both cooling ratios was also smaller in comparison to that when $t_{in} = 85$ °C. So, in this case (205 °C), the WVMFs at the last rows of the SHE remained higher than 8 %.

The DP temperature (Fig. 3a, dots 5 and 10) was also decreasing slowly along the test section and a larger decrease was obtained in the case of $R=4$. It should be noted that, when the cooling ratio was $R=1$, the DP temperature in rows no. 1 and 2 was very close to the tube wall temperature and, as is demonstrated in (Fig. 3b), there was no condensate collected from rows no. 1 + 2. Here convection was dominating and the ratio q_c/q_t was close to 100 %. Since there was no condensation in rows no. 1 + 2 all the water vapor mass was drawn to the further rows and began to condensate there. As the HA temperature was decreasing in the SHE, condensation from sections no. 3 + 4 and to the end of the section was gradually increasing. In this case, the ratio q_c/q_t was decreasing and thus indicating that the influence of convection was weakening through the experimental section. In the case of $R=4$ the tube wall temperature stayed much lower than the DP temperature, and therefore the condensation reaction occurred in all rows of the SHE (Fig. 3b). Even at the beginning of the test section and, even though the influence of convection was still strong ($q_c/q_t = 0.7$), there was some amount of condensate obtained in rows no. 1 + 2. Then, because of the previously mentioned reasons, in rows no. 3 + 6, the condensate flux increased and a slight decrease was obtained in the last rows (rows no. 7 + 8). At the end of the SHE, the convection was still playing an important role with 50 % from the total heat flux. This percentage is much higher than it was in the previous case for $t_{in} = 85$ °C.

Fig. 3. Temperature and WVMF (a), condensate flux and heat flux ratios (b) variation along the heat exchanger at $Re_{in} = 5000$, $t_{in} = 205$ °C, when the ratios of the cooling water flow rate to the HA inlet temperature are $R=1$ (curves 1–5): (1) average HA temperature, (2) average outside tube wall surface temperature, (3) cooling water temperature, (4) WVMF, (5) dew point temperature; when cooling ratio $R=4$ (curves 6–10): (6) average HA temperature, (7) tube wall temperature, (8) cooling water temperature, (9) WVMF, (10) dew point temperature.

4.1.3. Reynolds number 10000, HA inlet temperature 85 °C

At the Re_{in} number equal to 10,000 the HA was moving twice as fast as it did at $Re_{in} = 5000$ and thus spent half the time in the test section. These changes had some influence on how the temperatures distributed in the experimental section (Fig. 4a). There was a smaller decrease in the HA temperature (Fig. 4a, curves 1 and 6) through the section as well as a smaller increase in the cooling agent temperature (Fig. 4a, curves 3 and 6) compared to those obtained for the case of $Re_{in} = 5000$ (Fig. 2a). In general, at $Re_{in} = 10000$, the variation of the temperatures was similar to the already described with the temperatures determined in the case of $R=4$ being smaller than those at $R=1$. The DP temperature (Fig. 4a, dots 5 and 10) and the WVMF (Fig. 4a, curves 4 and 8) were gradually decreasing along the test section. However, the recorder decrease in the WVMF through the whole experimental section (Fig. 4a, curves 4 and 9) was even smaller (did not decrease below 8.4 % at $R=1$ and 8.2 % at $R=4$) than it was in the case of $Re_{in} = 5000$.

The tube wall temperature remained well below the DP temperature, which resulted in the presence of the condensate flux in all rows (Fig. 4a). At $R=1$ in rows no. 1 + 2 the condensate heat flux was small since here convection was as important as condensation ($q_c/q_t \approx 0.5$). Then, in the next rows (rows no. 3 + 4), the conditions were favourable for the condensation reaction (sufficient amount of water vapor, difference between the tube wall surface and HA temperatures), and the condensate flux increased. Until the end of the experimental section (rows no. 5 + 8) only a slight decrease in the condensate flux was observed and the influence of convection was decreasing. At $R=4$, the cooling agent had a lower temperature along the whole test section than it was at $R=1$ and thus created better conditions for condensation. In this case the influence of convection, especially in rows no. 1 + 4, was even smaller ($q_c/q_t \approx 0.35$) than it was at $R=1$.

4.1.4. Reynolds number 10000, HA inlet temperature 205 °C

At the higher HA inlet temperature (Fig. 5a), the variation of temperatures was very similar to the already described case with a temperature of 85 °C, and the absolute values were only a few degrees higher.

The WVMF in this case was also decreasing along the test section but did not decrease to a value smaller than 8.5 % even at the larger cooling ratio. Thus, this means that even a larger amount of water vapor does not condense in the SHE in comparison with the case when $t_{in} = 85$ °C.

As in rows no. 1 + 2 the difference among the DP temperature and tube wall surface temperature was the smallest (at $R=1$) compared to other rows of the SHE and, as a result, the condensate flux in rows no. 1 + 2 was also the smallest (Fig. 5b). Convection was prevailing in these rows ($q_c/q_t = 0.95$). Further, as the influence of convection was

Fig. 4. Temperature and WVMF (a), condensate flux and heat flux ratios (b) variation along the heat exchanger at $Re_{in} = 10000$, $t_{in} = 85$ °C, when the ratios of the cooling water flow rate to the HA inlet flow rate are $R=1$ (curves 1–5): (1) average HA temperature, (2) average outside tube wall surface temperature, (3) cooling water temperature, (4) WVMF, (5) dew point temperature; when cooling ratio $R=4$ (curves 6–10): (6) average HA temperature, (7) tube wall temperature, (8) cooling water temperature, (9) WVMF, (10) dew point temperature.

Fig. 5. Temperature and WVMF (a), condensate flux and heat flux ratios (b) variation along the heat exchanger at $Re_{in} = 10000$, $t_{in} = 205$ °C, when the ratios of the cooling water flow rate to the HA inlet flow rate are $R=1$ (curves 1–5): (1) average HA temperature, (2) average outside tube wall surface temperature, (3) cooling water temperature, (4) WVMF, (5) dew point temperature; when cooling ratio $R=3$ (curves 6–10): (6) average HA temperature, (7) tube wall temperature, (8) cooling water temperature, (9) WVMF, (10) dew point temperature.

constantly decreasing, the condensate flux was constantly rising. In the case of a larger cooling ratio ($R=3$) the influence of convection was smaller ($q_c/q_t = 0.7$) and the temperature difference was bigger which resulted in more pronounced condensation in rows no. 1 + 2 in comparison to that at $R=1$. In further rows, (rows no. 3 + 8), the condensate flux was distributed more equally and was similar as in rows no. 1 + 2.

4.2. Cooling ratio effect on condensation at WVMF=20 %

Experiments were performed with 20 % WVMF in order to learn the relation between the condensation process and the WVMF in the HA. The experiments were performed under similar conditions as described in paragraph 4.1 (i.e., CW ratio, HA inlet Re numbers and temperature remained the same).

4.2.1. Reynolds number 5000, HA inlet temperature 85 °C

At the larger WVMF there was almost no difference in the character of the temperature distributions along the experimental section in comparison to that at the smaller WVMF. The HA temperature was decreasing through the whole experimental section, and a more

pronounced decrease was also obtained in the case of $R=4$ (Fig. 6a, curves 1 and 6). The temperature of the cooling agent was rising from the inlet to the outlet, and it increased more in the case of $R=1$ than in the case of $R=4$ (Fig. 6a, curves 3 and 8). The change of the tube wall temperature (Fig. 6a, curves 2 and 7) was similar to that of the CW temperature at $R=1$ and, at $R=4$, the tube wall surface temperature had a somewhat “wavy” shape along the experimental section and resembled that obtained at the smaller WVMF (see Fig. 2a). However, at the WVMF of 20 %, more latent heat from the condensation was released and, as a result, the temperatures of the tube wall surface and cooling agent rose, while the HA temperature decrease in the SHE was smaller compared to the results obtained at WVMF=10 %.

The DP temperature in this case was about 64 °C (Fig. 6a, dots 5 and 10) and it was slowly decreasing along the SHE at both cooling ratios; the decrease at $R=4$ was larger than it was at $R=1$. Similar tendencies were obtained for the WVMF (Fig. 6a, curves 4 and 9), and here a larger decrease was also obtained at $R=4$.

Since the WVMF in this case was rather big (20 %) then, despite the fact that the tube wall temperature at the beginning of the SHE (i.e., at outflow) was also the highest, a condensate flux of about 17 kg/(h·m²)

Fig. 6. Temperature and WVMF (a), condensate flux and heat flux ratios (b) variation along the heat exchanger at $Re_{in} = 5000$, $t_{in} = 85$ °C, when the ratios of the cooling water flow rate to the HA inlet flow rate are $R=1$ (curves 1–5): (1) average HA temperature, (2) average outside tube wall surface temperature, (3) cooling water temperature, (4) WVMF, (5) dew point temperature; when cooling ratio $R=4$ (curves 6–10): (6) average HA temperature, (7) tube wall temperature, (8) cooling water temperature, (9) WVMF, (10) dew point temperature.

was obtained in the first rows (rows no. 1 + 2) at $R=1$ (Fig. 6b). Then, after some amount of water vapor had already condensed, the condensate flux decreased in rows no. 3 + 4. Further in the next rows, the condensate flux started to increase again as the tube wall surface temperature was decreasing (i.e., cold CW being supplied from row no. 8 to row no. 1) and this increased the condensation rate. Such condensate flux distribution was obtained for both cooling ratios. However, at $R=4$, the condensate flux was larger as the tube wall surface temperature remained much smaller.

The ratio q_c/q_t through the test section changed from 0.3 to 0.12 for both cooling ratios (Fig. 6b) indicating that the influence of convection was not significant and had a weakening tendency along the heat exchanger.

4.2.2. Reynolds number 5000, HA inlet temperature 205 °C

At the higher HA inlet temperature (Fig. 7a) the results were similar with the exception that the temperatures remained higher in the test section resulting in the fact that the conditions for condensation and for the release of latent heat were worse.

Indeed, the results show that at $R=1$ convection is dominating especially at the beginning of the test section where $q_c/q_t = 0.85$

(Fig. 7b). Despite that there was some condensate flux obtained from sections no. 1 + 2. Further, in rows 3 + 8, cold CW flow decreased the margin between the temperatures of the HA and tube wall and, as a result, the condensate flux was increased through the sections. When $R=4$, the tube wall temperature was well below that determined in the case of $R=1$, meaning that the influence of condensation in this case was stronger and q_c/q_t changes through the test section were small: from 0.48 to 0.4. Therefore, an almost equal condensate flux was obtained from rows no. 1 + 6, with a slight decrease in rows no. 7 + 8.

4.2.3. Reynolds number 10000, HA inlet temperature 85 °C

At $Re_{in} = 10000$ the HA flow rate was larger in comparison to that at $Re_{in} = 5000$, it cooled down less (Fig. 8a) and this weakened the release of latent heat. This meant that at both cooling ratios, water and tube wall surface temperatures were smaller than at $Re_{in} = 5000$ (cf. Fig. 8a and Fig. 6a). However, the differences in these temperatures were not substantial.

Since the HA inlet temperature was rather small ($t_{in} = 85$ °C) the condensation of water vapor was intensive and the contribution of convection was rather small; ratio q_c/q_t was changing in the range between 0.22 and 0.1 along the experimental section for both cooling

Fig. 7. Temperature and WVMF (a), condensate flux and heat flux ratios (b) variation along the heat exchanger at $Re_{in} = 5000$, $t_{in} = 205$ °C, when the ratios of the cooling water flow rate to the HA inlet flow rate are $R=1$ (curves 1–5): (1) average HA temperature, (2) average outside tube wall surface temperature, (3) cooling water temperature, (4) WVMF, (5) dew point temperature; when cooling ratio $R=4$ (curves 6–10): (6) average HA temperature, (7) tube wall temperature, (8) cooling water temperature, (9) WVMF, (10) dew point temperature.

Fig. 8. Temperature and WVMF (a), condensate flux and heat flux ratios (b) variation along the heat exchanger at $Re_{in} = 10000$, $t_{in} = 85\text{ °C}$, when the ratios of the cooling water flow rate to the HA inlet flow rate are $R=1$ (curves 1–5): (1) average HA temperature, (2) average outside tube wall surface temperature, (3) cooling water temperature, (4) WVMF, (5) dew point temperature; when cooling ratio $R=4$ (curves 6–10): (6) average HA temperature, (7) tube wall temperature, (8) cooling water temperature, (9) WVMF, (10) dew point temperature.

ratios (Fig. 8b).

Condensate was collected in every row of the experimental section. At $R=1$ the condensate flux was increasing through the whole experimental section (Fig. 8b) due to the decreasing tube surface temperature. At $R=4$ the tube wall surface temperature was much lower and less variable along the test section than at $R=1$ and therefore the obtained condensate flux was larger and more even.

4.2.4. Reynolds number 10000, HA inlet temperature 205 °C

Similar variations of the temperatures (Fig. 9a) and condensate fluxes (Fig. 9b) were obtained at the HA inlet temperature of 205 °C. In this case, at $R=1$, q_c/q_t equalled 0.7 at the beginning and decreased to 0.5 at the end of the experimental section. Whilst at $R=4$, the ratio q_c/q_t was smaller and the convection component decreased from 0.5 to 0.35.

4.3. Analysis and comparison of the results

4.3.1. Total and convection local Nusselt numbers

In this section, some typical results are presented. Local total Nu numbers' distribution at $Re_{in} = 5000$, WVMF=10 % and different cooling ratios are compared in Fig. 10a. At the cooling ratio $R=1$, Nu_t was constantly increasing from the beginning of the heat exchanger

(from $Nu_t = 45$) to row no. 4, and then started increasing more rapidly to the end of the heat exchanger, where it reached a maximum value of $Nu_t = 110$. The more rapid increase could be associated with the cold cooling water which supply to the experimental setup was realised from row no. 8. The results also show (Fig. 10a) that, at the cooling ratio $R=2$, the profile of the Nu_t distribution changed almost linearly. It started increasing from $Nu_t = 45$ at the beginning to $Nu_t = 75$ at row no. 6, where it stabilized and remained constant to the end of the SHE. The rise in the cooling ratio to $R=3$ and $R=4$ increased the Nu_t from the beginning to almost the middle of the test section in comparison to $R=1$ and, in the remaining part of the SHE, the Nu_t profile was similar to that at $R=1$. The increase in the Nu_t was due to the fact that the water in the case of $R=3$ and $R=4$ was moving much faster through the test section, and its temperature remained smaller than in the case of $R=1$.

At the beginning of the SHE, the influence of convection (Fig. 10b) in the case of $R=1$ and $R=2$ was close to that of the total heat transfer (i.e., $Nu_c \approx Nu_t$) and so the influence of condensation heat transfer in this part of the heat exchanger was small. This was confirmed by only negligible condensate flux at the beginning of the heat exchanger (see Fig. 3b) which happened because the cooling water spent a relatively long time in the heat exchanger, and by the time it reached the first rows, it had become hot. This resulted in the smallest Nu_t obtained under such

Fig. 9. Temperature and WVMF (a), condensate flux and heat flux ratios (b) variation along the heat exchanger at $Re_{in} = 10000$, $t_{in} = 205\text{ °C}$, when the ratios of the cooling water flow rate to the HA inlet flow rate are $R=1$ (curves 1–5): (1) average HA temperature, (2) average outside tube wall surface temperature, (3) cooling water temperature, (4) WVMF, (5) dew point temperature; when cooling ratio $R=3$ (curves 6–10): (6) average HA temperature, (7) tube wall temperature, (8) cooling water temperature, (9) WVMF, (10) dew point temperature.

Fig. 10. Comparison between variations of the local total Nu number (a) and convection Nu number (b) along the SHE at $Re_{in} = 5000$, various cooling ratios when the WVMF is 10 % and the HA inlet temperature is 205 °C.

conditions. In general, the variation of Nu_c was similar along the test section for all cooling ratios (Fig. 10b).

At $Re_{in} = 10000$ (Fig. 11a), WVMF=20 %, the Nu_t increased in comparison to that at $Re_{in} = 5000$ (Fig. 10a) due to a higher HA velocity in the SHE and WVMF, but the distribution profile remained the same. The Nu_c in this case (Fig. 11b) was also higher than that at $Re_{in} = 5000$ (Fig. 10b) and the results were the same as indicated above.

4.3.2. Average Nusselt numbers

The average Nusselt number dependency on the average Reynolds number, cooling ratio and HA inlet temperature is shown in Fig. 12. The general tendency is that at a smaller WVMF (Fig. 12a), the average \overline{Nu} number gradually increases with the increase in the \overline{Re} numbers (i.e. HA velocity and its stay time in the test section), in the whole Reynolds number range (3000–10000). With an increase in the cooling ratio, as the CW temperature through the section remains smaller, the \overline{Nu} number increases but the increase is rather small and the results lay in parallel to each other. It should also be noticed that \overline{Nu} number is less dependent on the \overline{Re} number at a smaller $t_{in} = 85$ °C and the dependency at a bigger $t_{in} = 145$ °C and 205 °C is more noticeable (Fig. 12a). The results also indicate that, at cooling ratios R=3 and R=4, the average Nusselt numbers were almost the same due to similar temperatures of the HA and cooling water obtained through the SHE. Generally, the decrease in the HA temperature from 205 °C to 85 °C (2.4 times) determined the increase in the average \overline{Nu} number by at least a factor of 2 over the whole \overline{Re} number range. In Fig. 12a, the average \overline{Nu} number for dry air in the Re_{in} range 5000–10000 is also presented. It is at least 2/3 of the value obtained with that found with the highest HA inlet temperature and the smallest cooling ratio.

The tendencies of \overline{Nu} distribution at WVMF=20 % (Fig. 12b) were similar to those described above, especially in the \overline{Re} number range between 5000 and 10000. Due to a higher WVMF in the humidified air passing the SHE, the increase in \overline{Nu} in this case was more expressed than it was at WVMF=10 % when the cooling ratio increased. This confirms a conclusion presented in [23] that the change in the Nusselt number becomes more pronounced at higher humidity levels. In the \overline{Re} number range between 3000 and 5000 (Fig. 12b), the increase in the \overline{Nu} number was less dependent on \overline{Re} in comparison to that at a smaller WVMF due to smaller influence of convection heat transfer. The results show that at WVMF=20 %, the average \overline{Nu} values are higher than at WVMF=10 %. However, the increase in the WVMF by a factor of 2 (from 10 % to 20 %) did not increase the \overline{Nu} by the same factor, i.e., the increase was between a factor of 1.2–1.6.

For the average Nu number, the uncertainties were calculated according to the [31] methodology. The maximum uncertainties obtained were up to 8 %.

The current investigation results in the case of the HA average Reynolds number $\overline{Re} = 5000$ –10000, WVMF mass fraction of 10 %–20 %, HA inlet temperatures 85 °C – 205 °C and cooling ratios R=1–4 were generalised by the equation:

$$\overline{Nu} = 3.28 \cdot \overline{Re}^{-0.5} \cdot WVMF^{0.68} \cdot \left(\frac{R^{0.07}}{\left(\frac{t_{f,in}}{t_{cw,in}} \right)^{0.92}} \right) \quad (19)$$

The above equation indicates that the average Nu is strongly dependant on the average Re and WVMF; a temperature ratio change (increase) has the opposite influence on the \overline{Nu} number and the effect of the cooling

Fig. 11. Comparison between variations of the local total Nu number (a) and convection Nu number (b) along the SHE at $Re_{in} = 10000$, various cooling ratios when the WVMF is 20 % and the HA inlet temperature is 205 °C.

Fig. 12. Comparison between average Nu numbers at various average Re numbers, HA inlet temperatures and cooling ratios at WVMF=10 % (a) and WVMF=20 % (b) with Nu numbers for dry air.

ratio is not very significant. The proposed equation generalizes the results with a maximum discrepancy of up to 15 %.

As it was indicated above, in [20], a relation for the average convection-condensation Nu number for the horizontal tubes bundle ($\varnothing 20 \times 2$ mm, 70 pcs.) was proposed:

$$\overline{Nu} = 0.1823 \overline{Re}^{-0.7707} \cdot Pr^{\frac{1}{3}} \cdot \overline{Ch}^{-0.2615}, \quad (20)$$

where \overline{Ch} is the condensation factor, $\overline{Ch} = \frac{\overline{t_{s(p)}} - \overline{t_w}}{\overline{t_f} - \overline{t_w}}$. Here $\overline{t_{s(p)}}$ is the saturation temperature based on the partial pressure of water vapor. Formula (20) is valid in the following range of parameters $\overline{t_w} = 16\text{--}30$ °C, $t_{f, in} = 150\text{--}250$ °C, $t_{cw, in} = 10\text{--}13$ °C, $t_{cw, out} = 24.6\text{--}36$ °C and $\overline{Re} = 3000\text{--}6000$.

In our case, only the CW inlet temperature was slightly higher in comparison with the CW inlet temperature used in [20]. To be able to compare our results with the data of [20] the condensation factor \overline{Ch} for our case was also evaluated using the partial pressure of water vapor in the heat exchanger. The average Nusselt and Reynolds numbers were recalculated based on the average temperatures for the heat exchanger.

The results obtained are presented in Fig. 13 by red dots and lines, additionally including the cooling ratio. The results are also presented in Table 1.

At $\overline{Re} = 3000$ and WVMF=10 %, the average \overline{Nu} almost corresponds

to our experimental data for the cases of R=2, R=3 and R=4 (Fig. 13a). Further, with the increase in the \overline{Re} number, the Nu obtained by Formula (20) indicates a stronger dependency on the \overline{Re} number (Fig. 13a). At WVMF=20 % (Fig. 13b), the data at $\overline{Re} = 3000$ for horizontal tubes had smaller values in comparison with our experimental data. With a further increase in the \overline{Re} , the data obtained by using Formula (20) also showed a stronger dependency on the \overline{Re} number; however, the \overline{Nu} values almost corresponded to that determined at $\overline{Re} = 5000$ and R=2. Thus, the comparison of the results revealed that there is some relation between the Nusselt numbers for vertical and horizontal tubes of the bundles.

4.3.3. Condensation efficiencies

The average condensation efficiencies for the serpentine heat exchanger increase with increasing cooling ratio, because the CW moves faster through the SHE and thus remains of the lower temperature, which has a strong effect on the condensation rate; however, some stabilization of condensation efficiency was obtained, most of the time from R=3 (Fig. 14). The highest condensation efficiencies were obtained at the smallest HA inlet temperatures and Re_{in} numbers (Fig. 14) as in this case the HA temperature is much closer to the dew point temperature and the HA also spent more time travelling through the SHE. At WVMF=10 %, $t_{in} = 85$ °C and $Re_{in} = 3000$ the condensation efficiency gradually increased from 35 % at R=1 to 45 % at R=3, i.e., by a factor of

Fig. 13. Comparison between average \overline{Nu} numbers at different average \overline{Re} numbers, HA inlet temperature $t_{in} = 205$ °C and cooling ratios at WVMF=10 % (a) and WVMF=20 % (b) with [20] for our data at R=2, 3, 4.

Table 1Comparison of the average \overline{Nu} numbers at different average \overline{Re} numbers and cooling ratios in the case of WVMF=10 % and 20 % with results presented in [20].

WVMF=10 %, $t_{in} = 205\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$				WVMF=20 %, $t_{in} = 205\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$			
Cooling ratio	Average \overline{Re} number	Average \overline{Nu} number (current study)	Average \overline{Nu} number [20]	Cooling ratio	Average \overline{Re} number	Average \overline{Nu} number (current study)	Average \overline{Nu} number [20]
1	3150	52.3	—	1	3130	68.2	—
	5190	66.5	—		5200	81.0	—
	10,360	85.5	—		10,300	121.3	—
2	3130	53.6	54.1	2	3100	86.0	—
	5190	67.4	79.5		5000	97.0	—
	10,390	87.4	—		10,300	135.9	—
3	3140	58.7	55.8	3	3050	89.1	58.7
	5190	73.72	83.1		5100	102.0	89.0
	10,340	94.9	—		10,200	142.3	—
4	3130	58.1	57.2	4	3050	87.0	60.3
	5190	74.3	85.0		5140	103.5	91.0

Fig. 14. Comparison between average condensation efficiencies at the WVMFs of 10 % (a) and 20 % (b), different cooling ratios, HA Re_{in} numbers and inlet temperatures.

about 1.3 (Fig. 14a). A further increase in the cooling ratio did not increase the condensation efficiency. As the HA temperature ($t_{in} = 205\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) increased, there was a decrease in the condensation efficiency for the same Reynolds number by about 10 % for all the cooling ratios in comparison to that at $t_{in} = 85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Similar tendencies were obtained at $Re_{in} = 5000$ (Fig. 14a). At the increased Re number ($Re_{in} = 5000$), the condensation efficiency even at $t_{in} = 85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was smaller by about 10 % for all cooling ratios compared to that at $t_{in} = 85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $Re_{in} = 3000$. At $Re_{in} = 5000$ and a higher HA inlet temperature, the condensation efficiency drastically decreased and, at $R=1$, it was less than half the size (i.e., it was 15 %); a further increase in the ratio to $R=2$ increased the condensation efficiency to almost 23 %. At $R=3$ and $R=4$, the condensation efficiency was not changing.

At a higher Re_{in} number ($Re_{in} = 10000$), the condensation efficiency decreased even more (Fig. 14a) and thus more non-condensed water vapor was drawn to the stack and released into the atmosphere. With a higher the Re_{in} number, the drop in the condensation efficiency became less evident for increased HA inlet temperatures (Fig. 14a, see results at $Re_{in} = 10000$, $t_{in} = 85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $205\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). Thus, in this case, the condensation efficiency was less “sensitive” to the HA inlet temperature.

The increase in WVMF to 20 % did not give any substantial increase in the condensation efficiency (cf. Fig. 14a and Fig. 14b) but, of course, the amount of the collected condensate was increased. At $t_{in} = 85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $t_{in} = 205$ and $Re_{in} = 3000$, the maximum condensation efficiencies were almost the same as in the case of WVMF=10 %. The increase in the condensation efficiency associated with the increase in the cooling ratio was better expressed at WVMF=20 % than at WVMF=10 %.

At $t_{in} = 85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $Re_{in} = 5000$, the efficiency (Fig. 14b) even decreased by about 5 % points (i.e., to 30 %) instead of that which was at the WVMF of 10 %. For $t_{in} = 85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $Re_{in} = 5000$, as well as for $t_{in} = 205\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $Re_{in} = 10000$, the peak values starting from the cooling ratio $R=2$ were similar, with a maximum condensation efficiency of about 25

% at cooling ratio $R=3$. A further increase in the HA inlet temperature to $205\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at $Re_{in} = 10000$ resulted in a decrease in the efficiency by a factor of approximately 3/4 (to $\sim 20\%$).

The results show that the largest condensation efficiency of 35 % was obtained when the WVMF was 10 %. The increase in the WVMF to 20 % did not give better results at any cooling ratio. Therefore, as more water vapor is supplied in the case of WVMF=20 % in comparison to that at WVMF=10 %, the condensation efficiency even slightly decreases, because the SHE is not able to condensate more water vapor. The most optimal cooling ratio for the SHE in terms of condensation efficiency and heat transfer in this case is $R=3$. The results obtained on cooling ratio and condensation efficiency match those presented in [25], where it was shown that the largest condensation efficiency was obtained in the case of the cooling ratio equal to 3 and an increase in the ratio to 4 did not increase the condensation efficiency.

For all the experimental cases, an analysis of heat balances ($Q_t = Q_{cw}$) was performed. The relative uncertainty for the balance was determined as $\Delta = ((Q_t - Q_{cw})/Q_{cw}) \cdot 100$. The results of the maximum relative uncertainties presented in Fig. 15 show that the uncertainties were between 8–9 %. For other cases, the uncertainties were in the range between 2.5–7.8 %.

5. Conclusions

The analysis of hot air, containing 10 % and 20 % of water vapor mass fraction (WVMF), condensation in different rows of the serpentine type heat exchanger (SHE) at different air inlet temperatures ($85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $145\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $205\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), inlet Re numbers (3000, 5000 and 10000) and cooling ratios (between cooling water and humidified air; $R=1, 2, 3$ and 4) allowed drawing such conclusions:

Fig. 15. Heat balances with the largest uncertainties.

- The results have shown that with an increase in the cooling ratio the condensate flux increased in different sections of the heat exchanger, and the increase was more pronounced in the first rows (rows no. 1–4) in comparison to that in the last rows (rows no. 5–8).
- The convection heat flux (q_c) to total heat flux (q_t) ratio was strongly dependent on the HA inlet Re number, temperature and WVMF. Convection heat flux could be almost 100 % ($Re_{in} = 10000$, WVMF=10 %, $t_{in} = 205$ °C) at the beginning of the SHE and then decrease to 50 % at the end of SHE.
- The local total Nu number usually increased with higher cooling ratio. The convection Nu number showed little dependence on the cooling ratio and in most analyzed cases remained constant along the test section.
- The most optimal operation of the heat exchanger in terms of condensation efficiency and heat transfer in the analyzed range of the inlet parameters was determined to be at the cooling ratio $R=3$.
- Increased cooling ratio determined the increase in the average Nu number for both HA inlet temperatures and the WVMF; however, the average Nu number was more dependent on an increase in the average Re number than on the cooling ratio.
- The obtained results from the practical point of view will provide an extended basis for the optimisation of the design of heat exchangers for waste heat recovery in the cases of different cooling water flow rates. It could also be applied to validate computational models developed for condensation heat transfer and condensate flux numerical modelling along heat exchangers.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Robertas Poškas: Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Arūnas Sirvydas:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Mohab Salem:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Povilas Poškas:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Hussam Jouhara:** Writing – review & editing, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgment

This work was partly funded by the European Union H2020 programme project iWAYS under grant agreement number 958274.

References

- J.J. Fierro, A.E. Atehortua, C.N. Londoño, M. Giraldo, H. Jouhara, L.C. Wrobel, Evaluation of waste heat recovery technologies for the cement industry Int. J. Thermofluids. 7–8 (2020) 100040, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijft.2020.100040>.
- B. Egilegor, H. Jouhara, J. Zuazua, F.A. Mansour, K. Plesnik, L. Montorsi, L. Manzini, ETEKINA: Analysis of the potential for waste heat recovery in three sectors: Aluminium low pressure die casting, steel sector and ceramic tiles manufacturing sector, Int J. Thermofluids. 1–2 (2020) 100002, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijft.2019.100002>.
- C.A.M. Porto, J.J. Fierro, C.N. Londoño, L. Lopera, A.E. Atehortua, M. Giraldo, H. Jouhara, Potential savings in the cement industry using waste heat recovery technologies, Energy 279 (2023) 127810, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.127810>.
- H. Jouhara, D. Bertrand, B. Axcell, L. Montorsi, M. Venturelli, S. Almahmoud, M. Milani, L. Ahmad, A. Chauhan, Investigation on a full-scale heat pipe heat exchanger in the ceramics industry for waste heat recovery, Energy 223 (2021) 120037, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.120037>.
- Y.C. Shih, Y.C. Lee, K.C. Lin, Optimized design on the thermohydraulic performance of the helical coil heat exchanger, Int. J. Thermofluids 17 (2023) 100271, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijft.2022.100271>.
- W. Li, S. Kadam, Z. Yu, Heat transfer enhancement of tubes in various shapes potentially applied to CO₂ heat exchangers in refrigeration systems: Review and assessment, Int. J. Thermofluids 20 (2023) 100511, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijft.2023.100511>.
- P. Prajapati, B.D. Raja, H. Savaliya, V. Patel, H. Jouhara, Thermodynamic evaluation of shell and tube heat exchanger through advanced exergy analysis, Energy 292 (2024) 130421, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.130421>.
- Poškas R., Sirvydas A., Mingilaitė L., Jouhara H., Poškas P. Experimental investigation of water vapor condensation on flue gas in different rows of a heat exchanger model Thermal Science and Engineering Progress. ISSN: 2451-9049. (2024), Vol. 47. 102365. [10.1016/j.tsep.2023.102365](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsep.2023.102365).
- Poškas R., Sirvydas A., Mingilaitė L., Poškas P., Jouhara H. Investigation of effect of cooling water characteristics on flue gas condensation along vertical tube heat exchanger Energy. ISSN: 0360-5442. (2024), Vol. 289. 130046. [10.1016/j.energy.2023.130046](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.130046).
- T. Fujii, H. Uehara, Laminar filmwise condensation on a vertical surface. Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer 15 (1972) 217–233, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0017-9310\(72\)90070-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0017-9310(72)90070-1).
- T. Fujii, U. Haruo, K. Chikatoshi, Laminar filmwise condensation of flowing vapour on a horizontal cylinder, Int. J. Heat Mass Transf. 15 (1972) 235–246, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0017-9310\(72\)90071-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0017-9310(72)90071-3).
- A.P. Kryukov, V.Y. Levashov, Condensation from a vapor-gas mixture on a plane surface, Heat and Mass Transfer and Physical Gasdynamics 46 (2008) 700–704, <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0018151X08050167>.
- Rose JW. Effect of pressure gradient in forced convection film condensation on a horizontal tube. Int J. Heat Mass Transfer (1984), Vol. 27, p. 39–47. [10.1016/0017-9310\(84\)90235](https://doi.org/10.1016/0017-9310(84)90235).
- M.M. Shah, A general correlation for heat transfer during film condensation inside pipes. Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer 22 (4) (1979) 547–556, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0017-9310\(79\)90058-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0017-9310(79)90058-9).
- Jakob M. Heat transfer, chapter theory of film condensation of vapor at rest on cylindrical surfaces, vols. 667–673. John Wiley & Sons; 1949.
- M. Joachimiak, D. Joachimiak, P. Krzyślak, Analysis of heat flow in a tube bank of a condenser considering the influence of air, Archives of Thermodynamics 38 (3) (2017) 119–134, <https://doi.org/10.1515/aoter-2017-0019>.
- T. Fujii, H. Uehara, K. Hirata, K. Oda, Heat transfer and flow resistance in condensation of low pressure steam flowing through tube banks, Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer 15 (1972) 247–260, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0017-9310\(72\)90072-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0017-9310(72)90072-5).
- China Electricity Council. Beijing: China Market Press; 2013.
- V. Bespalov, L. Beljaev, D. Melnikov. MATEC web of conferences, Using Air for Increasing the Depth of the Flue Gas Heat Recovery, 2015, No. 37.
- D. Che, Y. Da, Z. Zhuang, Heat and mass transfer characteristics of simulated high moisture flue gases, Heat Mass Transf. 41 (3) (2005), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00231-004-0505-9>.
- L. Yongbin, Ch. Defu, K. Yanbin, Effect of vapor condensation on forced convection heat transfer of moistened gas, Heat Mass Transf. 43 (2007) 677–686, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00231-006-0148-0>.
- Y. Wang, J. Jiao, Y. Dai, Z. Ke, Q. Zhao, F. Li, Study on heat transfer characteristics of flue gas condensation in narrow gap heat exchangers, Therm. Sci. 27 (6A) (2023) 4681–4693, <https://doi.org/10.2298/TSCI221125117W>.
- A. Arshan, M.H. Atta, B. Fahad Rafi, G. Shahbaz, A. Imran, Numerical Analysis of Impact of Relative Humidity on Crossflow Heat Exchangers with Staggered Configuration at Maximum Operating Temperature, Int. J. of Innovations, Science & Technology 3 (4) (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1109/IBCAST54850.2022.9990263>.
- E. Wang, K. Li, N. Husnain, D. Li, J. Mao, W. Wu, T. Yang, Experimental study on flue gas condensate capture and heat transfer in staggered tube bundle heat

- exchangers, *Appl. Therm. Engineering* 141 (2018) 819–827, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2018.06.035>.
- [25] K. Jeong, M.J. Kessen, H. Bilirgen, E.K. Levy, Analytical modelling of water condensation in condensing heat exchanger, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 53 (11–12) (2010) 2361–2368, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2010.02.004>.
- [26] N. Mohammadaliha, M. Amani, M. Bahrami, A Thermal-hydraulic assessment of condensing tube bank heat exchangers for heat and water recovery from flue gas, *Appl. Therm. Engineering* 15 (2022) 118976, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2022.118976>.
- [27] K. Yang, J. Yang, Y. Da, L. Han, L. Deng, D. Che, A numerical study on convective condensation of flue gas in tubular heat exchangers, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* (2024) 122524, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2024.122524>.
- [28] D. Teng, X. Jia, W. Yang, L. An, G. Shen, H. Zhang, Experimental investigation into flue gas water and waste heat recovery using a purge gas ceramic membrane condenser, *ACS Omega* 7 (2022) 4956–4969, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.1c05610>.
- [29] X. Li, H. Chen, Z. Li, H. Zhang, Condensation heat transfer characteristics of flue gas moisture recovery using ceramic membranes, *J. Membr. Sci.* 680 (2023) 121762, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2023.121762>.
- [30] R. Poškas, A. Sirvydas, M. Salem, P. Poškas, H. Jouhara, Experimental investigation of water vapor condensation from hot humidified air in serpentine heat exchanger, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer* (2024) 125068, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2023.125068>.
- [31] N.C. Barford, *Experimental measurements: Precision, error and truth*, 2nd ed., John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1985.